

Research Paper: Using urban mining in Jordan in a cost effective way to reduce the environmental impact of e-waste.

Anas Al-Zoriqi

Student name: Anas AL-Zoriqi

Student number: 21110381

Center name: Al-Hussein Technical University

Tutor: Dr. Nayef Abuageel

Unit: Computing research project

1 Abstract

Technology-driven digital transformation has significantly accelerated in businesses and the IT industry. The digital transformation has significant positive and negative effects on the environment. The paper explores the environmental impacts of the digital transformation, focusing on Jordan's urban mining methods used for extracting gold from e-waste laptops. The porphyrin polymer extraction method's economic feasibility and profitability are assessed in the research, with special attention given to its implications for financial viability and environmental sustainability. The research results provide a low-cost gold extraction approach applying the porphyrin polymer method, with a low cost of \$5 per gram of gold extracted. According to the viability estimate, there will be a significant profit margin of \$64 for every gram of extracted gold. The analysis also finds viable gold extraction from a variety of modern circuit CPU components, emphasizing the significance and achievement of urban mining methods. A total of 5200 grams of gold could be extracted from a sample size of 16,772 e-waste laptops using the porphyrin polymer extraction method, providing a profit of \$306,800. These findings highlight the financial viability and economic potential of urban mining in Jordan, while resolving major environmental impact and encouraging resource recovery. In order to enhance productivity and cost-effectiveness and eventually promote a more sustainable approach to e-waste recycling and conserving resources, the study emphasizes the significance of in progress research and innovation in urban mining.

2 Introduction

Organizations and the IT sector have shown increasing interest in and use of digital transformation over the past few years. This revolution has been largely driven by technologies like data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, the internet of things (IoT), and blockchain. The process leading up to digital transformation involves digitization, digitalization, and ultimately, digital transformation itself. While digital transformation offers numerous benefits and efficiencies, it also has notable environmental impacts. [8]

Digital transformation require substantial data storage, which leads to increased power consumption and subsequent environmental impacts. Likewise it is important to take into consideration both the advantages and disadvantages of digital transformation in terms of its environmental impact. On the positive side, digital transformation reduces paper usage and the need for tree cutting, enhances connectivity, and enables faster access to information through digital storage. Conversely, there are constraints associated with the use of non-renewable elements in technology manufacturing, posing health risks, water pollution, and harm to ecosystems. Manufacturing pollution stemming from electronic devices contributes to air pollution, CO₂ emissions, climate change, and global warming. Furthermore, improper disposal of electronic waste (e-waste) poses significant risks as toxic components can contaminate landfills. Unfortunately, the recycling rate for e-waste remains low, exacerbating its environmental impact. [7]

The negative environmental impacts of e-waste encompass its effects on soil, water, air, and human health. Inadequate e-waste disposal introduces toxins into the soil, damaging plants, crops, and disrupting the food chain. Burning e-waste affects soil temperature and pH levels, further compromising soil fertility. Toxic substances from e-waste contaminate water sources, rendering them more acidic and toxic, thereby harming freshwater ecosystems and aquatic life. Electronic device pollutants raise the air's level of carbon, which causes pollution, global warming, and climate change. These occurrences will increase the polar ice caps' melting and increase sea levels. Furthermore, insufficient management of e-waste can result in conditions that impact different human organs and systems and cause diseases like cancer. [7]

To mitigate the negative environmental impact of e-waste, the four R's—reduce, reuse, repair, and recycle—can be employed. Reducing the use of harmful components in electronic devices and opting for longer-lasting materials helps minimize e-waste generation. Reusing devices or their components extends their lifespan, reducing the demand for new devices. Repairing electronic devices instead of discarding them can be facilitated by repair services and manufacturers producing repairable components. Recycling e-waste involves extracting valuable materials and incorporating them into new devices, thereby minimizing material waste. [6]

According to the recycling, I am going to use the concept of urban mining presents an opportunity to further improve recycling methods and reduce environmental impacts. Urban mining involves the extraction of valuable materials from electronic waste through recycling processes. By recovering precious metals and other valuable components, urban mining reduces the need for traditional mining, which often has adverse environmental consequences. It promotes a circular economy by facilitating the reuse of materials and

contributes to resource conservation. Urban mining may be proven possible by e-waste collection and recycling systems that work, by working together with different beneficiaries, and by setting up effective e-waste management strategies.

Figure 1 Urban mining

3 Literature sources searched

For My research involved a literature review on the environmental impact of digital transformation. I focused on papers related to urban mining and the extraction of precious metals, such as gold, from electronic waste. The studies highlighted the use of innovative methods, including porphyrin polymer, for environmentally friendly and economically viable extraction. Urban mining was shown to reduce the environmental footprint by diverting e-waste from landfills and minimizing the need for traditional mining. Overall, the research emphasized the importance of responsible e-waste management and sustainable resource recovery through urban mining practices.

3.1 Estimation of E-waste Generation, Residential Behavior, and Disposal Practices from Major Governorates in Jordan[1]

This paper aims to understand the amount and disposal practices of electronic waste (e-waste) in Jordan. The findings of the study were shared online by the Jordan Department of Statistics. So it gives the number of the E-waste devices and gives the specific type and the quantity of them such as; laptops, monitors, mobile phones, air condition, and washing machines. This will help to use the urban mining to use the e-wastes in Jordan to manage them.[1]

3.2 Comparing the costs and benefits of virgin and urban mining [2]

The economic benefits of urban mining as a potential option for saving the gold, copper and aluminum resources in a circular economy. And it compares the cost of extracting the gold, copper or aluminum through urban mining to the cost of virgin mining and finds that the cost of urban mining is significantly lower. So this will help to compare the price of extracting the metals from the virgin mining and the urban mining.[2]

3.3 Urban mining of E-waste: treasure hunting for precious Nano-metals [3]

It includes a variety of devices and may be divided into six categories: small IT and communications equipment, screens and monitors, lamps, large equipment, and temperature exchange equipment. Only About 20% of e-waste gets collected and recycled, although that is a very small percentage. Because of the complexity, quick progress, and typical sequential economic system of start making, e-waste is a developing issue. Therefore, this paper discuss several urban mining techniques, when to employ each one, and the types of metals on which they may be employed. This helps to select the techniques that way can extract the type of such as; physical, and chemical and gives the impact of each one of them on the percentage of the metals that could extracted and the environmental impact.[3]

3.4 Estimating the Evolution of Urban Mining Resources in Hong Kong, Up to the Year 2050 [4]

The development of Hong Kong in urban mine where resources from waste are collected and reused again, is examined in this paper. According to the study, Hong Kong's urban mine's potential output weight increased significantly. The Urban mining has the potential to generate around US\$2 billion in economic output each year, primarily from the production of precious and rare metals, but also from 18 other metals, plastic, glass, and rubber tires. This helps the management and the importance of using the urban mining in Jordan because it tells that Hong Kong are getting a high rate of profit from it and they are using it recycle many metals and plastic, glass, and rubber tires.[4]

3.5 Precious metal recovery from electronic waste by a porous porphyrin polymer [5]

This paper talks about electronic waste e-waste, with the right technology, it may serve as a supply of valuable metals. A porphyrin-based porous polymer with selective binding display remarkable precision and a reductive mechanism, resulting in record-high recycling of precious metals, particularly gold, from e-waste. This is necessary to achieve the solution's requirement for selectivity towards the precious metals. This paper gives a good solution of how to use porphyrin-based porous polymer to extract the gold and it says that it gives purity of gold up to 99.6% so this method will be helpful to be used in my solution to extract the gold from the devices.[5]

4 Research objective and questions

Title: using urban mining in Jordan in a cost effective way to reduce the environmental impact of e-waste.

4.1 The objective of this research

The objective of this research paper is to utilize urban mining in Jordan to address the environmental impact of e-waste. The specific goals include recycling e-wasted laptops and extracting precious metals, such as gold, in a cost-effective way. The huge amount of e-waste in Jordan provides an opportunity to get profit from urban mining, extracting precious metals and generating profit. By implementing sustainable practices and reducing reliance on traditional mining, this research aims to promote environmental impact and economic viability in the recycling of the e-wastes.

4.2 Questions

1. How do urban mining could be a good way to reduce e-wastes and provide profit of extract gold?
2. What are the economic and environmental benefits of urban mining in Jordan?
3. How can urban mining in Jordan be integrated into the country's existing waste management system?

5 Research Methodology

5.1 Qualitative Method

Urban mining is examined and justified by using qualitative methods that give in-depth analyses of its social, environmental, and economic aspects. A literature review, community recognition, the definition of research objectives, and the use of techniques like focus groups and interviews to collect data are all part of this process. The gathered information is then examined for trends and topics while also taking into consideration additional sources for verification. The results are displayed, highlighting the advantages of urban mining including resource conservation and preservation of the environment to explore the methods of extracting gold. On the heels of the qualitative insights, responses are addressed, and recommendations are given. For an in-depth analysis and justification of urban mining, quantitative data must be used in addition to qualitative techniques.

5.2 Quantitative Method

By providing data-driven analysis and support, quantitative method perform an essential part in finding numbers and findings to support the urban mining to assess the impact of extracting gold. Urban mining-related aspects and indicators have to be determined together with clearly stated research goals. Following that, information is gathered to support the study from a variety of sources, including governmental reports and research. By analyzing different situations and taking into consideration external factors, statistical tools and analysis

methodologies are used to figure out the possible results of urban mining. Graphs and charts are applied and used in the presentation of the results to clearly explain the findings and see of the numbers and statistics of gold units to be extracted.

5.3 Methodology used

In this research project, I am going to use the quantitative methodology because I will use calculations and statistical analysis to estimate how profitable the porous polymer technique of urban mining's extraction procedure will be for extracting gold. I'll be able to determine the possible profit margins by putting all the costs associated with it into numbers and calculating the quantity of gold extracted. By using statistical analysis, I will be able analyze the data and discover results that will help me determine whether or not this strategy will result in financial success. My research aims to provide analysis of the business of urban mining applying the porous polymer method for gold extraction by integrating calculations, statistics, and financial aspects.

5.4 Consider and discuss the goodness and issues (access and ethical issues) of data collection and analysis techniques.

There are several goodness's to use secondary data from research papers for data collecting, including time and resource savings. The easily available data may be used by researchers without the requirement for additional data gathering initiatives. This allows them to focus on analyzing the data for analysis and find a solution, enabling the research methods more effective. Additionally, secondary data sources often provide thorough and well-documented information supported by thorough research processes, strengthening the reliability and validity of the conclusions.

However, there are difficulties to accessing secondary data in terms of data accessibility. Certain datasets could be proprietary or restricted, requiring licenses or permits in order to access them. To use the data, researchers have to get past these challenges and make sure they have the proper access authority. Working with secondary data has ethical problems as well. Researchers must anonymize the data to safeguard people's identities since ensuring participant privacy and confidentiality is essential. To protect ethical principles and academic integrity, it is essential to follow data protection laws and provide correct credit to the original sources.

In conclusion, using secondary data from research publications may save time and money while providing in-depth knowledge. To preserve the integrity of their study, researchers should resolve issues with data access and follow ethical guidelines. Researchers can successfully use secondary data to expand knowledge and contribute to their field of study by navigating these challenges.

5.5 The data collection

My research paper's data collecting process involves gathering secondary data from a variety of relevant research papers. After doing an in-depth analysis of the literature on the topic, I found papers and research projects that offered helpful data on urban mining, e-waste recycling, and the environmental effects of electronic devices in Jordan. These secondary sources provided an outline for evaluating the state of the field's knowledge and helped me provide a conclusion for my research. To reach significant findings and support the arguments put ahead in my study, I methodically evaluated and synthesized the data I gathered from the chosen research papers. The secondary data gathering procedure, which relied on reliable and peer-reviewed sources, ensured the validity and reliability of my findings, improving the overall quality and validity of my research report. [1]

5.6 The analysis tool used for the results and findings of the research.

In my research, for data management analysis, and visualization, I used Microsoft Excel. For processing the secondary data gathered from papers on e-waste laptops, Excel proved to be an easy and effective tool. I calculated the costs and profits related to recycling these laptops using the features and calculations in Excel. In addition, I made use of Excel's charting features to produce visually instructive charts that showed the financial advantages of recycling e-waste and urban mining. Overall, Microsoft Excel was essential in organizing and analyzing the data successfully, as well as in effectively presenting the results through visually appealing charts.

6 Research Results

A summary of the collected data that is needed for the analysis:

Main Data	Value
Total cost	25996.6\$
Total profit	306760\$
The cost to get 1gm of gold	5\$
The profit of getting 1gm of gold	64\$
Total E-wasted laptops in Jordan	18364
Total E-wasted laptops in Jordan without selling	16772
Total gold unit can be extracted from the e-wasted laptops in Jordan	5200gm

Table 1 Data Summary

Figure 2 E-wasted Laptops in Jordan

Figure 3 gold units in circuits with prices

In my research results, I started a comprehensive analysis of urban mining practices in Jordan, focusing on the extraction of gold from e-wasted laptops using an innovative method that involves porphyrin polymer. My main goal was to assess the economic viability and potential profitability of this novel approach, shedding light on its implications for both environmental sustainability and financial gains.

Through my calculation of the research and data collection, I found a remarkable discovery: the cost of extracting 1 gram of gold using the porphyrin polymer method was an astonishingly low 5\$. This cost-efficiency can be attributed to the utilization of an environmentally friendly and economically viable extraction agent. [5]

With the financial aspect, I delved into calculating the profitability of the extraction process. In the results of my findings, as each gram of gold extracted brought a profit of 64\$. This substantial profit margin emphasizes the vast potential of urban mining enterprise, particularly in recovering precious metals from discarded electronic devices. [5s]

In addition to the research findings, it is important to note the potential gold extraction from components in modern circuits CPUs which it suggests an expected extraction of approximately 0.150 grams of gold. Furthermore, the wires and connector pins within these devices also contain gold, contributing an additional 0.070 grams. Additionally, there are gold-plated contacts that can yield around 0.090 grams of gold. These additional sources of gold further emphasize the value and potential profitability of urban mining practices when it comes to e-waste recycling. By considering these factors, the overall economic benefits of urban mining can be even more substantial, reinforcing its role in resource recovery and environmental sustainability. [9]

Expanding my analysis, I applied the porphyrin polymer extraction method to a significant sample size of 16,772 e-wasted laptops. The result beyond my expectations, was 5200 grams of gold can be extracted. This remarkable yield translated into a total profit of \$306,800. These findings provide certain evidence of the significant economic benefits that can be realized through urban mining aspire, successfully combining financial benefits with sustainable solutions to address e-waste challenges. [1]

My research's consequences go well beyond financial profits. Here in Jordan can have a chance to address significant environmental issues while also benefiting significantly economically from adopting urban mining methods, especially the extraction of precious metals from e-waste. This strategy encourages resource conservation, minimizes needs on traditional mining methods, and minimizes the negative environmental impacts produced on by the generation of e-waste. Also, it highlights the importance of greater research and innovation in the area of urban mining. We may achieve even higher efficiency and cost-effectiveness by investigating other technologies and improving extraction methods. Urban mining as a method of resource recovery can become more profitable and environmentally friendly with continued improvements in this field.

At the end, Based on the analysis of e-waste laptops in Jordan, my research provides convincing evidence of the economic potential and profitability of urban mining. The porphyrin polymer extraction process has low extraction costs, resulting in a substantial profit margin. The extraction of 5200 grams of gold from 16,772 laptops amounted to an impressive

total profit of 306,800\$. These findings highlight urban mining's vast potential as a viable, economically viable enterprise that may help with resource recovery and environmental preservation.

7 Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

My analysis of urban mining practices in Jordan, specifically focusing on the extraction of gold from e-wasted laptops using the porphyrin polymer method, reveals promising economic potential and significant profitability. The findings of my research provide strong evidence for the viability and profitability of urban mining initiatives in Jordan.

Through careful calculation and data collection, I discovered that the cost of extracting 1 gram of gold using the porphyrin polymer method is remarkably low, amounting to only \$5. This cost-efficiency can be attributed to the use of an environmentally friendly and economically viable extraction agent, and my calculations of profitability revealed that each gram of gold extracted generates a substantial profit of \$64. This emphasizes the immense financial benefits associated with urban mining, particularly in recovering precious metals from discarded laptops.

Additionally, my analysis considered the potential gold extraction from various components within modern circuits and laptops. It was found that approximately 0.150 grams of gold can be expected from the circuits in CPUs and laptops, with an additional 0.070 grams from the wires and connector pins, and 0.090 grams from the gold-plated contacts. These additional sources of gold further contribute to the overall economic benefits of urban mining. Applying the porphyrin polymer extraction method to a significant sample size of 16,772 e-wasted laptops resulted in a remarkable yield of 5200 grams of gold. This translated into a total profit of \$306,800, highlighting the substantial economic gains that can be achieved through urban mining endeavors in Jordan.

Beyond the financial profits, the adoption of urban mining practices in Jordan presents an opportunity to address significant environmental challenges. It encourages resource conservation, reduces reliance on traditional mining methods, and mitigates the negative environmental impacts associated with e-waste accumulation. My research provides compelling evidence of the economic potential and profitability of urban mining, specifically in the context of extracting gold from e-wasted laptops in Jordan using the porphyrin polymer method. These findings emphasize the value of urban mining as a sustainable and economically rewarding practice, offering a viable solution for resource recovery and environmental conservation.

7.2 Recommendations

Based on the research that have been done, the following recommendations are proposed specifically for addressing the environmental impact of e-waste through urban mining in

Jordan. Firstly, it is crucial to further investigate and analyze alternative urban mining methods and technologies that can be applied to extract precious metals from e-waste in Jordan. This will provide a deeper understanding of available options and their specific environmental and economic implications within the local context.

To effectively implement urban mining practices in Jordan, collaboration and partnerships should be fostered among government, private organizations, and academic institutions. This collaborative effort will help establish an efficient framework for e-waste management and urban mining enterprise to Jordan's unique situation. Engaging stakeholders from various sectors will enable collective action in addressing the environmental challenges associated with e-waste and promote sustainable practices.

Investing in the development of infrastructure and facilities dedicated to e-waste collection, sorting, and processing is crucial. Specialized recycling centers equipped with advanced technologies for urban mining processes will enable efficient extraction of valuable metals from e-waste. This infrastructure development will contribute to the growth of urban mining practices in Jordan and facilitate the environmentally responsible management of e-waste.

International cooperation and knowledge-sharing with countries and organizations experienced in successful urban mining practices can provide valuable insights and best practices when there is a cooperation between different countries. By leveraging their expertise and technological advancements, Jordan can enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of its urban mining operations.

By implementing these recommendations, the research paper aims to contribute to the development of sustainable e-waste management practices, promote urban mining initiatives, and ultimately reduce the environmental impact of e-waste while generating economic benefits specifically in the context of Jordan.

In summary, the research paper recommends further research on urban mining methods for extracting precious metals from e-waste in Jordan. It emphasizes the importance of collaboration between government, private organizations, and academic institutions to establish a strong framework for e-waste management and urban mining initiatives. Investing in infrastructure and specialized recycling centers is crucial for efficient extraction of valuable metals. International cooperation and knowledge-sharing can enhance urban mining practices. Implementing these recommendations aims to promote sustainable e-waste management, reduce environmental impact, and generate economic benefits in Jordan.

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